

CSR COMMUNICATION MODEL AS A SUSTAINABLE SOCIAL INNOVATION IN PRIVATE OWNED ENTERPRISE IN INDONESIA (CASE OF PROGRAM OF KALBE FARMA IN PANDAWA LIMA VILLAGE)

MIRANA HANATHASIA^{1*}, ANNISA FITRIANA LESTARI² and MOCHAMMAD KRESNA NOER³

^{1,2,3}Universitas Bakrie, Kawasan Rasuna Epicentrum, Kuningan, Jakarta Selatan.

*Corresponding Author Email: mirana@bakrie.ac.id

Abstract

Sustainability has become a critical issue in 21st-century business due to the ongoing exploitation of natural resources. Various organizations and private sectors are working together to create initiatives that support environmental, social, and economic futures. The concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) emerges as both a form of corporate accountability and a role of Public Relations in engaging stakeholders. CSR development involves identifying community needs and shaping programs that require targeted communication. This study aims to analyze innovations in CSR activities related to environmental and social issues through the CSR Communication Model. The research focuses on the CSR program of one of private owned enterprise in Indonesia, PT Kalbe Farma in Wonogiri, Central Java. Using a case study method, data were collected through interviews with Kalbe Farma's CSR team and local stakeholders. The findings reveal that Kalbe's CSR innovations are based on community needs, implemented strategically with strong communication and transparency, and support corporate sustainability through empowerment, collaboration, and effective stakeholder engagement.

Keywords: CSR Communication, Sustainability, Corporate Social Responsibility, Stakeholders.

INTRODUCTION

Without proactive and collective efforts from all segments of society, the Earth's ecosystem cannot be expected to function effectively or endure in the long term. In recent 21st century, sustainability has become a central concern in the business world, driven by growing awareness of the environmental impact caused by human exploitation of natural resources.

Sustainability does not rely solely on industries or businesses themselves; it is also heavily influenced by society; both those who work within industries and those who exist outside of them (Bell & Morse, 2003, as cited in Bagherzadeh & Manoli, 2012).

The growing attention among organizations toward achieving sustainability has been reinforced by the emergence of the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). CSR refers to the accountability of both profit and non-profit organizations for their impacts on stakeholders, the natural environment, and the broader community.

It emphasizes corporate accountability and transparency in actions that encompass social, ethical, environmental, and economic initiatives, many of which are voluntary and extend beyond market and commercial transactions (Riano & Yakovleva, 2020).

In practice, the formulation and implementation of a company's CSR initiatives are typically handled by the Corporate Communication or Public Relations (PR) department. CSR communication focuses on both external and internal messaging directed toward various stakeholders, and thus consistently falls within the scope of corporate PR responsibilities (Coombs & Holladay, 2011).

In addition to global CSR challenges, there are specific issues shaped by each country's policies, economic conditions, and environmental contexts. For a company to be a good, responsible, and sustainable corporate actor while also gaining competitive advantage, it must take a step further by adopting innovative approaches (Bagherzadeh & Manoli, 2012).

PT Kalbe Farma is a healthcare products company based in Indonesia. In alignment with its core business, Kalbe Farma is committed to contributing toward the realization of sustainable business practices. The company communicates this commitment through the tagline *Bersama Sehatkan Bangsa* ("Together for a Healthier Nation").

To support its implementation, Kalbe has developed a Sustainability Governance framework, which includes an organizational structure, policies, frameworks, and strategies covering nine core areas, articulated through its internal (ERAT) and external (SEHAT) pillars (Kalbe Farma, 2021). Internally, Kalbe applies the ERAT Pillar—*Etos* (Ethos), *Raga* (Body), *Asa* (Hope), and *Tindak* (Action).

Externally, the SEHAT Pillar encompasses: *Sains dan Teknologi Kesehatan* (Health Science and Technology), *Ekosistem dan Kelestarian Lingkungan* (Ecosystems and Environmental Sustainability), *Hidup Sehat dan Pendidikan Kesehatan* (Healthy Living and Health Education), *Akses Layanan Kesehatan* (Access to Health Services), and a *Total Ekosistem Bisnis Berkelanjutan* (Total Sustainable Business Ecosystem).

These pillars have been mapped to support seven priority Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), namely Goals 1, 3, 4, 7, 9, 10, and 12—with a primary focus on Goal 3: "Good Health and Well-being."

Kalbe Farma has implemented its sustainability initiatives through one of its CSR programs by providing access to clean water in Wonogiri, Central Java (Pratiwi, 2023). This CSR initiative is part of a social innovation program called *Desa Pandawa Lima*—which stands for *Pancasilais* (*Pancasilais*), *Damai* (*Peaceful*), *Berwawasan Lingkungan* (*Environmentally Conscious*), and *Mandiri* (*Independent*) Villages.

The development of clean water infrastructure began in 2013 and remains ongoing, having reached 112 households to date. Continuous innovation in CSR programming is key to Kalbe Farma's sustainability success. It all started with free medical treatment and health education programs in three areas in Wonogiri, which later led to insights from a local community about the urgent need for clean water access—sparking a sustainable initiative in response.

Through this CSR program in Wonogiri, Kalbe Farma received two awards at Indonesia Social Responsibility Award (ISRA) on 2023 (Dahono, 2023). In the same year, a local hero from *Desa Pandawa Lima* also earned the Environmental & Social Innovation Award (ENSIA).

Kalbe Farma was recognized for its success in empowering the local community by providing training, financial support, and economic growth opportunities.

The success of Kalbe Farma and the local hero in developing the CSR program cannot be separated from the communication strategy involved. Communication occurred at every stage of the CSR process—from stakeholder mapping and needs identification to the communication of the CSR initiative itself.

To achieve sustainability goals, companies must be reformed, redesigned, and restructured to minimize their ecological impact on society at large (Shrivastava, 1995 in Bagherzadeh & Manoli, 2012).

A sustainability strategy enables companies to set new rules and be rewarded by stakeholders based on the level of responsibility they demonstrate (Willard, 2005 in Bagherzadeh & Manoli, 2012). CSR strategies should enable businesses to achieve their goals while engaging stakeholders in the implementation of meaningful CSR initiatives (Coombs & Holladay, 2011).

Coombs and Holladay outline a five-stage CSR strategy process: 1) Scanning and monitoring; 2) Conducting formative research; 3) Creating the CSR initiative; 4) Communicating the CSR initiative; 5) Conducting an evaluation and providing feedback. To further enrich this model, the fourth stage—communicating the CSR initiative—is expanded by incorporating insights from Kim (2019). The revised model identifies five factors that influence how CSR messages are conveyed from organizations to the public: CSR informativeness, personal relevance, consistency, transparency, and a factual message tone.

When a company creates a positive impact on society and the environment, it signals the presence of well-crafted policies aimed at demonstrating its commitment to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) (Bagherzadeh & Manoli, 2012).

This process requires that social responsibility objectives be prioritized through continually evolving policies, daily operational procedures, and overall corporate activities. In doing so, the company can move toward sustainability and shape its operations to be more environmentally friendly.

Innovation within the CSR context refers to the creation of new approaches that add value to both the company and its stakeholders—and is a key factor in maintaining competitive advantage (Dimitrova, 2020). CSR initiatives drive innovation through social, environmental, and sustainability approaches that generate new products, services, and strategies.

Corporate communication plays a crucial role in managing stakeholder relationships, building reputation, and distributing information that encourages action and dialogue. Companies are expected to maintain transparency and serve as mediators that bridge social values. According to the 4A concept by Prahalad et al. (2012), innovative CSR should include *awareness*, *access*, *affordability*, and *availability* to create a broad and sustainable impact.

Therefore, this study aims to analyze how innovation within CSR activities, particularly those related to the environment and community, can drive a company toward sustainability through the lens of the CSR Communication Model?

Figure 1: CSR Innovation in Process and Communication Model

(Source: Coombs & Holladay (2011); Kim (2019))

METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a qualitative approach with a case study design, in line with the objective of exploring in depth the CSR program of PT Kalbe Farma in Pandawa Lima Village, Wonogiri. A qualitative approach seeks to explore individuals or groups and understand the social issues they experience (Creswell, 2014). This method was chosen because it enables the researcher to thoroughly comprehend the processes, events, and relationships between the company and its stakeholders in creating sustainability through CSR innovation. The object of this study is Kalbe Farma's CSR initiative focused on providing clean water access in Pandawa Lima and Boto Villages. The research subjects include various parties directly involved in the program, such as CSR managers, project officers, local community leaders (also known as local heroes), and village residents. Data collection was carried out using two primary methods: in-depth interviews and literature review. In-depth interviews were used to uncover subjective experiences and perspectives from informants, while literature review was conducted to obtain a theoretical foundation and support the field findings (Rutledge & Hogg, 2020).

The data analysis followed several stages (Taherdoost, 2020), including transcribing the interviews, thoroughly reading the data, coding, organizing codes into themes, and writing interconnected descriptive narratives. Finally, data interpretation was performed by comparing interview findings with literature references and relevant theories to draw meaningful conclusions. To ensure data validity, the researcher applied source triangulation techniques, which involved cross-verifying findings through different data collection methods. This technique was intended to enhance the study's credibility and ensure that the results objectively reflect real field conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Implementation of CSR Process Model

According to Coombs and Holladay (2011), the CSR process model consists of five key stages in developing a strategic CSR initiative.

1. Scanning and Monitoring phase, where a company identifies emerging social and environmental issues and monitors stakeholder interests and responses toward its CSR initiatives. The following table illustrates informants' perspectives regarding the implementation of the scanning and monitoring phase:

Table 1: Informants' Perceptions on the Implementation of Scanning and Monitoring

Participants	Comments
AN	"...our entry into Wonogiri was not based on business motives, but we entered because of issues identified in their mapping —water, to be specific..."
	"...we tried to identify which individuals looked promising... from religious leaders, small communities..."
	"...every three months we conduct evaluations... we visit the area directly so we can see if there are any obstacles..."
	"...we consulted with the community leaders... we needed to hold a meeting with residents or not... we held FGDs at the community hall..."
T	"...every year... we certainly carry out program evaluations... if it's difficult or impossible, then we'll find an alternative..."

(Source: Author's Compilation)

Several excerpts from the interviews reflect the early identification of social-environmental issues and ongoing monitoring of stakeholders' needs and responses:

- a) Initial identification of community needs through social mapping. This represents the scanning process where Kalbe identified clean water as a primary need before designing the program.
- b) Social mapping and identification of local heroes. This step reflects Kalbe's efforts to understand the social structure and identify key local actors who could support program success.
- c) Regular monitoring and routine evaluations. These indicate active, on-the-ground monitoring to assess the program's sustainability and community responses.
- d) FGDs to monitor stakeholder perceptions and interests. This shows Kalbe's commitment to listening to stakeholder input through open and inclusive forums.
- e) Adjusting strategies based on monitoring outcomes. This highlights how feedback is used to adapt the program to ensure relevance and effectiveness.

Interview results suggest that Kalbe implements a systematic approach in scanning social and environmental issues, followed by continuous monitoring to align the program with stakeholder needs and expectations. These findings align with research by Willya Achmad (2021), which emphasized that monitoring and evaluating community empowerment-based

CSR programs significantly affect the program’s success. Such efforts are essential for ensuring business continuity, fostering harmonious relations with the community, and securing strong social support.

2. Conducting Formative Research. Formative research was conducted to gather the necessary information to ensure the CSR program was designed appropriately and effectively. The following are excerpts from informants that reflect this phase of the process:

Table 2: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Conducting Formative Research

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“...our entry into Wonogiri was not based on business motives, but we entered because of issues identified in their mapping —water, to be specific...”</i>
	<i>“...we tried to identify potential local figures who already seemed reliable... we started by approaching formal leaders, and then moved on to the informal ones...”</i>
	<i>“...we held discussions and FGDs to reach an agreement—like whether Mas Teo would become the head and who would take the treasurer role...”</i>
	<i>“...we truly did genba, actual field visits... then we evaluated everything formally back at the head office...”</i>
	<i>“...at first, we already had program experience in Banten... then we developed and adapted it based on the conditions in Wonogiri...”</i>

(Source: Author’s Compilation)

The excerpts above illustrate the initial collection efforts (such as data, social mapping, and community feedback) to ensure that the CSR program would be appropriately aligned with the community’s needs:

- a) Social mapping to identify the community’s needs before program design. This clearly illustrates a formative research process that involves identifying key community issues, in this case, the need for clean water.
- b) Identification of local figures through informal social observation. This represents an early form of qualitative research aimed at recognizing key local actors who can support the program’s success—a critical component of community-based formative research.
- c) The use of FGDs to collect local insights. Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) serve as a formative research method to gather aspirations and reach a community consensus prior to program implementation.
- d) Direct field observation and reflection. *Genba* (on-site observation) is part of the formative process to ensure that program planning aligns with the socio-geographical realities.
- e) Utilizing previous experience as a foundation. Kalbe adopted lessons learned from prior initiatives as baseline data to inform the development of new programs in other regions.

Interview findings indicate that Kalbe conducted formative research through social mapping, FGDs, field observation, and a review of past experiences. These components formed a crucial foundation for designing a CSR program that was contextual, effective, and aligned with local

needs. This aligns with research conducted by Intani (2018), which suggests that CSR implementation by public relations practitioners involves a series of planning stages, including formative analysis, execution, and—although not always comprehensively—evaluation. Both internal and external communication and engagement activities are key success factors in the strategic implementation of CSR initiatives.

3. Creating the CSR Initiative. The company begins to concretely design and shape its CSR initiatives, ensuring that the programs are aligned with community needs and can be effectively communicated. The following statements from informants provide insights into this phase:

Table 3: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Creating the CSR Initiative

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“...our entry into Wonogiri was not based on business motives, but we entered because of issues identified in their mapping —water, to be specific... So, from the very beginning, our focus was on addressing water issues...”</i>
	<i>“...we eventually adopted the concept of Creating Shared Value (CSV). So, when communicating the program, it became clear that the initiative was part of our business strategy.”</i>
	<i>“...we follow the PDCA model (plan, do, check, act). In the planning phase, we formed local community groups... then allowed them to operate independently for a while...”</i>
	<i>“...we provided health education, waste management facilities, community group development, animal feed processing, and livestock training...”</i>
	<i>“...when we speak to the public, we emphasize the community benefits. We also use social media, IG Live, and other platforms to communicate...”</i>

(Source: Author’s Compilation)

The excerpts above reflect how the company begins to concretely develop CSR initiatives with the aim of addressing actual needs and facilitating effective communication:

- a) Program development based on actual community needs. This demonstrates that CSR initiatives are shaped by the most urgent issues identified during the initial community mapping phase.
- b) Adoption of the Creating Shared Value (CSV) concept. The CSR programs are not only meant to meet societal needs, but are also strategically aligned with the company’s business goals and positioned as such in communication efforts.
- c) Structured planning with clear stages and objectives. The CSR initiatives are developed through a systematic managerial approach, starting with the establishment of organized community structures.
- d) Translation into tangible, localized initiatives. CSR activities move beyond abstract ideas, being transformed into concrete local programs relevant to community needs.
- e) Tailored communication strategies for effectiveness. Kalbe considers how to effectively communicate its CSR programs to ensure clarity and resonance with both the public and other stakeholders.

The interview findings indicate that Kalbe’s CSR initiatives are designed in a concrete, structured, and needs-based manner, with a strong emphasis on strategic communication. This aligns with the study by Octaviani, Raharjo, and Resnawaty (2022), which emphasizes that effective CSR implementation must be intertwined with community empowerment efforts—achieved, in part, through well-crafted communication strategies.

4. Communicating the CSR Initiative. This stage focuses on disseminating information so that stakeholders understand and support the CSR initiatives, using appropriate content and media. The following are statements from informants related to this phase:

Table 4: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Communicating the CSR Initiative

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“We are always supported by other divisions, particularly external communications, to jointly craft messages we can convey externally... we are highly attentive to the choice of media and our target audience...”</i>
	<i>“...we utilize multiple communication channels, including social media, digital platforms, website, and a dedicated Kalbe sustainability microsite...”</i>
	<i>“The public is now quite familiar with CSR... it certainly enhances company awareness and reputation... leading to greater stakeholder trust...”</i>
	<i>“...we focus primarily on highlighting the benefits to the community... we present both our social and environmental programs in language that is very accessible...”</i>

(Source: Author’s Compilation)

The quotes above highlight how information is disseminated to stakeholders to foster understanding and support, using tailored content and strategic media:

1. Strategic selection of media and target audiences. Kalbe carefully selects communication channels and adapts its messaging to the specific characteristics of each audience.
2. Utilization of multiple communication platforms. A wide range of media are employed to ensure consistent and broad outreach to various stakeholder groups.
3. Communication aimed at building public understanding and support. CSR messaging is intended to foster a positive perception of the company, build trust, and encourage stakeholder endorsement.
4. Content adaptation to ensure public engagement and persuasion. Kalbe customizes the language and content of its CSR communications to ensure clarity and relevance for the general public.

Interview results show that Kalbe has implemented CSR communication strategies that prioritize clarity, accessibility, and effective outreach. This aligns with the findings of Aurelia, Arismayanti, and Anggraini (2023), who emphasize that CSR must be communicated effectively to the public in order to build a positive corporate image and reputation—both essential for corporate sustainability. Selecting the appropriate communication channels is thus a crucial tool for aligning CSR messaging with the company’s broader goals.

5. Conducting an Evaluation and Providing Feedback. This stage involves assessing program outcomes to determine their impact, guide future improvements, and inform the direction of subsequent CSR initiatives. The following are excerpts from informant interviews:

Table 5: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Conducting an Evaluation and Providing Feedback

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“...we conduct evaluations every three months... although community groups submit written reports... the most effective method is still direct visits...”</i>
	<i>“...in our next visit, we always provide feedback to the community groups... we truly follow the PDCA cycle — plan, do, check, act...”</i>
	<i>“...we still can't answer when or how we'll exit... we're continuing to explore social innovation there, but there's no exit plan yet...”</i>
T	<i>“...we conduct a mid-year evaluation every year. If something is not working, we let it go... and shift our focus elsewhere...”</i>

(Source: Author’s Compilation)

These statements reflect how program evaluation serves as a foundation for improvement and guides future CSR implementation:

- a) Regular and structured evaluations. Kalbe carries out scheduled evaluations to monitor program sustainability and inform adjustments as needed.
- b) Evaluation as a basis for follow-up actions and improvements. Assessments are not merely reviews but are used as references for corrective actions and ongoing program development.
- c) Evaluation as a measure of success and strategic refinement. This process provides reflective insights into the program’s effectiveness, informing decisions on whether to continue or terminate initiatives.
- d) Evaluation as a foundation for future strategy. Evaluation results are integral to long-term planning and exit strategy.

The interview findings demonstrate that evaluation plays a vital role in Kalbe’s CSR cycle. It serves not only to assess program effectiveness but also as a basis for improvement and strategic planning for future implementation. This is consistent with the study by Taliding (2021), which asserts that continuous evaluation is essential to measure the effectiveness of CSR initiatives. Evaluations support informed decision-making, whether to discontinue, continue, or further develop specific aspects of the implemented programs.

The Implementation of CSR Communication Model

Kim (2019) identifies eight key factors that influence the effectiveness of communication in CSR programs to ensure alignment with stakeholder expectations.

1. CSR Informativeness, refers to the importance of conveying information about CSR programs commitment, objectives, impact, and context. Interview findings reveal that:

Table 6: Informants’ Perceptions of CSR Informativeness Implementation

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“When speaking to the general public, we don’t highlight the business impact much... instead, we emphasize the benefits for the community.”</i>
	<i>“It started with clean water... then we added health education... waste management... economic empowerment... and then tree planting... because we’re also thinking about how to count the carbon absorption...”</i>
	<i>“...everything is supported with valid evidence... receipts and such... to support our claims, which we include in the sustainability report.”</i>
	<i>“...the communication channels range from social media, digital media, the website, and a dedicated Kalbe microsite for sustainability.”</i>

(Source: Author’s Compilation)

These statements highlight the importance of four key dimensions of informativeness in CSR communication:

- a) CSR commitments and objectives. Communication efforts are tailored to the audience, focusing on relevance and resonance.
- b) Narratives of impact and relevance. The messaging includes detailed storytelling about the program’s effects, spanning health, environment, and the economy.
- c) Importance of documentation and verification. Emphasis on transparent records supports accountability and reinforces trust.
- d) Use of diverse communication channels. A multichannel strategy enhances public access and openness.

The interviews illustrate that Kalbe not only implements CSR activities but also communicates them with intentionality, ensuring that stakeholders perceive the program as both impactful and trustworthy. These findings are in line with Saleh and Sihite (2020), who argue that CSR initiatives must be communicated effectively as a form of corporate accountability and as part of broader community empowerment efforts.

2. Third-Party Endorsement, where support or statements from external parties enhance the credibility of CSR messages and public trust. Interviews with various informants revealed the following insights:

Table 7: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Third-Party Endorsement

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“The local government has been very supportive of Kalbe so far, because from the beginning, we involved them and sought permission... it also contributes to the KPIs of the Environmental Agency... they benefit as well.”</i>
D	<i>“Thanks to Mas Arie, Mas Abi, and Kalbe. I really feel helped, they’re incredibly kind. Their communication is excellent, inclusive, and they’re very close to us. You can feel they genuinely care.”</i>

	<i>"We trust Mas Theo because he provided clean water facilities... Mas Arie also helped with development. Pak Abi often visits during events, just to observe."</i>
T	<i>"They [Kalbe] also provide guidance and monitoring... so it can be sustainable... not just a one-time donation and then leaving."</i>

(Source: Author's Analysis)

These quotes illustrate how endorsements from third parties (such as community members, local authorities, or influential figures) can significantly enhance the credibility of CSR messages and foster public trust:

- a) Endorsement from local government (external legitimacy): Direct support from local authorities reinforces the legitimacy and credibility of Kalbe's CSR initiatives.
- b) Endorsement from impacted community members (grassroots credibility): Testimonials from beneficiaries reflect a high level of trust in Kalbe and serve as authentic endorsements.
- c) Local heroes as trust brokers: The involvement of respected local figures acts as a bridge between Kalbe and the community, strengthening trust through personal credibility.
- d) Recognition from trusted local sources (local hero): Endorsements from credible third-party actors (local heroes) reinforce the sustainability and integrity of Kalbe's CSR programs.

The interview findings highlight the mechanism of third-party endorsement, where validation from external, non-corporate actors becomes essential for building public trust. This aligns with the findings of Kiroyan (2019), who emphasized that third-party endorsement strengthens corporate CSR communication by enhancing message legitimacy—provided that the endorsing party is credible, independent, and not commercially tied to the company.

3. Personal Relevance, where CSR messages aligned with individuals' personal experiences or interests are more likely to be accepted. Interviews with various informants revealed the following insights:

Table 8: Informants' Perceptions on the Implementation of Personal Relevance

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>"...we entered because of issues identified in their mapping—water, to be specific... So, from the very beginning, our focus was on addressing water issues..."</i>
D	<i>"The clean water distributed can be used for livestock too... Now it's much easier, just turn on the tap."</i>
	<i>"I used to be unemployed, now I can work... This is women's empowerment. The change is really tangible."</i>
	<i>"Every afternoon there used to be conflicts over water distribution... eventually, they all joined [Kalbe's program]."</i>
	<i>"Pak Theo and Kalbe needed help, and I needed income. So, it's mutually beneficial... For the next project by Mas Theo... the women were enthusiastic."</i>

(Source: Author's Analysis)

These narratives show how CSR messages and programs that are personally relevant to the community’s needs and lived experiences are more likely to be accepted and adopted:

- a) Clean water as a direct community need: The alignment of CSR activities with daily necessities like clean water ensures immediate relevance and acceptance.
- b) Economic empowerment as personal transformation: The CSR program directly addresses life experience, especially for women, offering tangible life improvements.
- c) Response to past conflict over resources: Previous negative experiences (e.g., water conflict) amplify the perceived value and relevance of CSR solutions.
- d) Community participation driven by economic and social relevance: Personal and economic motivations drive enthusiastic engagement with CSR initiatives.
- e) Programs tailored to local context: Rather than one-size-fits-all, CSR efforts are informed by local needs assessment, ensuring higher personal relevance.

These findings reinforce the importance of designing CSR initiatives around the real-life experiences and needs of the community. This supports the study by Nurozi & Sisdianto (2024), which found that companies employing a needs-based resource strategy are more likely to generate a meaningful social impact. Understanding local context and unique community needs is essential for effective CSR design and implementation.

4. Self-Efficacy, referring to the audience’s belief in their ability to contribute to the CSR program, which enhances participation and impact. Interviews with various informants revealed the following insights:

Table 9: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Self-Efficacy

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“As locals, we collect the waste... we get free milk... That was purchased by Mas Teo from us.”</i>
D	<i>“From the start, we were clearly trained by professionals. They offered skills training... Now we’re used to evaluating how we manage the maggots.”</i>
	<i>“I used to be unemployed, now I can work... This is women’s empowerment.”</i>
T	<i>“Now we can fund new wells independently... we’re able to operate on our own.”</i>
	<i>“Every year we have activities... training or motivational events... we even use the remaining monthly funds for this.”</i>

(Source: Author's Analysis)

These excerpts reflect the community’s growing belief in their capacity to contribute, which in turn fuels program participation and effectiveness:

- a) Empowerment through skills training. Kalbe’s training programs enhance community members’ capabilities and confidence, particularly in areas like maggot farming.
- b) Women actively participating in economic roles. Increased self-efficacy leads to greater involvement, especially among women, who now view themselves as contributors.

- c) Community engagement in exchange-based systems. Mechanisms such as trading waste for milk instill a sense of meaningful contribution to the CSR cycle.
- d) Independent water management and collective organizing. Community-run initiatives demonstrate collective self-efficacy and reduced dependency on Kalbe.
- e) Community involvement in evaluation and ideation. Residents feel a sense of ownership, actively contributing ideas and feedback for program development.

These findings suggest that Kalbe’s CSR programs foster self-confidence and a sense of agency within the community, encouraging active participation and shared ownership. This aligns with the findings of Ernawati (2022), which emphasized that when communities feel a sense of ownership over CSR initiatives, they are more likely to support, maintain, and sustain them over time.

- 5. Self-Promotional Message Tone, referring to how communication may be informative but also subtly promotional, influencing public perception. Interviews with various informants revealed the following insights:

Table 10: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Self-Promotional Message Tone

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“...we didn’t claim that the waste-to-milk program in Wonogiri was just a way to promote Entrasol... we focused more on its social benefits.”</i>
	<i>The waste-to-milk program needs proper calculation... we saw sales increase in Wonogiri area... animal medicine purchases too... so there’s business value we leveraged.”</i>
	<i>“In 2023, we received a gold proper award... this helped convince the BOD that the program truly benefits the business.”</i>
	<i>“...social media, digital platforms, website, Kalbe’s sustainability microsite... such as Kalbe CSR... where we showcase our social programs, including awards.”</i>
	<i>“From the beginning, Kalbe had to comply with many regulations... thankfully, we’ve had no incidents or negative records.”</i>

(Source: Author's Analysis)

These statements reflect how the tone of communication can be both informative and subtly self-promotional, shaping public perception of the company:

- a) Subtle promotional tone in social programs. Although presented as community benefits, CSR messages subtly incorporate product branding.
- b) Linking CSR to business outcomes. Statements connecting CSR to increased sales reveal underlying promotional motives.
- c) Highlighting achievements to promote reputation. External recognition is used to reinforce Kalbe’s image and signal CSR program success.
- d) Use of media platforms for image promotion. Kalbe consciously leverages public channels to disseminate CSR content and promote its corporate image.

- e) Highlighting internal excellence as self-promotion. Emphasis on compliance and integrity reinforces Kalbe’s image as a trustworthy and competent company.

These findings demonstrate how Kalbe blends informative content with a promotional tone in its CSR communications—an approach that strategically shapes public perception. This supports the study by Syaifudin et al. (2023), which found that CSR communication plays a dual role: it informs stakeholders while also enhancing the company’s image and economic contribution, particularly among underserved communities.

- 6. Frequency, which refers to the regulation of CSR message delivery frequency to prevent public skepticism due to perceived overexposure. Interviews with various informants revealed the following insights:

Table 11: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Frequency

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“...when speaking to the public, we emphasize the social benefits... we don’t say that exchanging waste for milk is also a way to sell Entrasol milk...”</i>
	<i>“...we use very simple, layman’s language... we only mention around 10 or 20 percent of the business impact. The rest—80 percent—is about the benefits to society.”</i>
	<i>“...IG Live sessions are open to the public... we do talk about these programs—of course, in very accessible language.”</i>
	<i>“...even the waste-for-milk program... will eventually hit a saturation point.”</i>

(Source: Author's Analysis)

These quotes highlight efforts to manage the frequency and tone of CSR communication to avoid perceptions of insincerity or excessive self-promotion:

- a) Awareness of boundaries when discussing business impact. Kalbe deliberately limits business-related messages to maintain sincerity and avoid public suspicion.
- b) Strategic limitation of business-related messaging. CSR communications are carefully balanced to focus on social impact rather than overt business gains.
- c) Evaluation and adjustment of repetitive messaging. Kalbe actively monitors message repetition to prevent fatigue or skepticism from the audience.
- d) Recognition of audience fatigue from frequent messaging. Even operationally strong programs may lose effectiveness if over-communicated, suggesting the need for message timing and variation.

The interview findings demonstrate that Kalbe exercises conscious control over the frequency, content, and emphasis of CSR communication to maintain perceived sincerity and prevent overclaiming.

This is in line with the findings of Syahrani et al. (2018), who emphasize that effective CSR communication should be trustworthy, informative, educational, and free from emotional exaggeration.

7. Consistency, referring to the alignment and continuity of CSR messages with corporate values and long-term objectives. Interviews with various informants revealed the following insights:

Table 12: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Consistency

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“...we eventually adopted the CSV concept... that these activities are part of the business... sustainability must co-exist with the business.”</i>
	<i>“...the tone of communication isn’t overly cheerful... we don’t say the waste-for-milk program is also about selling milk... but the community already understands—we say it’s about empowerment.”</i>
	<i>“...we really follow a PDCA pattern: plan-do-check-act... we conduct evaluations every three months.”</i>
	<i>“...we currently don’t have an exit strategy for Wonogiri... in fact, we’re continuing to introduce new social innovations there.”</i>
	<i>“We prefer to get information first from local heroes, like the community leaders.”</i>

(Source: Author's Analysis)

These statements reflect the coherence and sustainability of Kalbe’s CSR messaging and practice across internal and external stakeholders:

- a) Program continuity aligned with corporate values (Creating Shared Value). CSR is integrated with Kalbe’s business strategy, reflecting a consistent narrative across functions.
- b) Message alignment between internal and external audiences. Tailored messages are still aligned in substance, maintaining coherence in public and internal communications.
- c) Consistent monitoring and evaluation practices. Structured and ongoing assessment ensures that program delivery aligns with long-term CSR goals.
- d) Long-term community commitment. Kalbe avoids short-term interventions, demonstrating sustainable engagement and program expansion.
- e) Consistent use of community representatives (local heroes). Utilizing local leaders as message intermediaries ensures sustained and structured communication flow.

The interviews indicate that Kalbe’s CSR programs are implemented with consistency—in messaging, practice, and community engagement. This aligns with the findings of Lim & Jiang (2021), who argue that consistent CSR communication contributes to authenticity, which in turn strengthens trust and long-term commitment in organizational-public relationships.

8. Transparency, which involves openness regarding both the successes and challenges of CSR programs, forming the foundation of public trust and corporate credibility. Interviews with various informants revealed the following insights:

Table 13: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Transparency

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“...even the waste-for-milk program can reach a point of saturation... that’s when we start evaluating it.”</i>
	<i>“We planted trees... some were taken, some mangoes didn’t ripen before the trees disappeared... we can’t control everything 100%...”</i>
	<i>“...the treasurer is usually open... shares financial reports, how much came in and went out, and the narrative behind it.”</i>
	<i>“We never donate money directly, just to be clear... funds must be managed by the community group... never in the form of direct cash.”</i>
T	<i>“Kalbe... doesn’t just provide support... they also monitor... if there are challenges, they try to help however they can.”</i>

(Source: Author's Analysis)

These quotes reflect transparency in CSR practices, including acknowledgment of limitations, financial openness, and collaborative monitoring:

- a) Openness about challenges and program limitations. Kalbe is transparent not only about successes but also about difficulties and the need for program evaluation.
- b) Honesty about loss and lack of control in the field. Admitting limitations in oversight reinforces credibility and transparency.
- c) Financial transparency within the community. Both Kalbe and community stakeholders engage in open reporting, fostering mutual trust.
- d) Clarity in the form of assistance (non-cash). Kalbe ensures transparency in its aid delivery to prevent misunderstandings or misuse.
- e) Transparency in monitoring and evaluation outcomes. Open dialogue about program progress and challenges reinforces accountability.

These findings demonstrate Kalbe’s commitment to transparency as a core value in CSR execution and communication, which in turn builds trust and strengthens relationships with stakeholders. This supports the conclusions of Sendlhofer & Tolstoy (2022), who argue that transparency in CSR plays a vital role in establishing sustainable, trust-based relationships with stakeholders.

The Role of the CSR Communication Model in the CSR Process Model

CSR communication factors are closely related to the “*communicating the CSR initiative*” stage within the CSR process model. At this stage, the company’s primary goal is to effectively convey its CSR initiatives to stakeholders to foster understanding, support, and even active participation in the programs. Interview findings suggest that among the eight dimensions of the CSR Communication Model, transparency emerged as the most dominant.

Transparency reflects openness in communication, encompassing both successes and challenges, and serves as the foundation for building long-term stakeholder trust. In the

implementation of its CSR initiatives, Kalbe has demonstrated a strong commitment to transparency through several practices:

1. Commitment to information disclosure. Kalbe actively shares both the successes and obstacles of its programs with the public and stakeholders, showing that openness is a core strategy in cultivating trust.
2. Open reporting systems within the community. The assisted communities also adopt transparency principles, indicating that this value is deeply embedded across all levels of CSR implementation.
3. Transparent communication of program impacts and benefits. Kalbe presents a truthful account of how programs are carried out, including the logistical and economic flows behind the CSR activities.
4. Planned and clear communication strategies. The company does not obscure the business aspects of its programs but delivers them in a transparent manner that maintains positive public perception.
5. Monitoring as a tool for transparency: Kalbe directly involves residents in data collection, discussions, and follow-up actions, reinforcing transparency across all stages of communication.

Transparency stands out as the most significant factor in the *communicating the CSR initiative* phase due to its practical application throughout the program, its emphasis in both internal and external communications, and its role in fostering public trust and enhancing corporate credibility. This finding is consistent with the study by H. Kim and Lee (2018), which identifies transparency in CSR communication as a strategic necessity for strengthening consumer trust.

However, among the eight communication factors, frequency remains an area for improvement and further development. Frequency governs how often messages are delivered, playing a crucial role in maintaining public awareness without causing fatigue or suspicion. The need for enhancement in this area stems from several observations:

1. Potential public fatigue with the program. Programs that are communicated or executed too frequently without renewal may lead to reduced engagement and community burnout.
2. Lack of strategy in message variation and channel use. While channels are in place, there is no evidence of planned content frequency, campaign cycles, or narrative refreshment. Without this, messages risk becoming monotonous or even distrusted.
3. Awareness of overexposure risk without supporting strategy. Although Kalbe recognizes the risk of appearing overly self-promotional, there is little indication of a structured effort to determine when and how often messages should be delivered to keep them fresh and credible.

4. Limited data on communication schedules or calendars. There is no indication that Kalbe employs a cyclical communication system, event-based messaging, or seasonal CSR storytelling, which are essential for maintaining effective message delivery.

Improving the frequency dimension is crucial due to early signs of audience fatigue, the absence of a strategic approach to timing and intensity of communication, and the potential for poorly managed frequency to trigger public skepticism.

This aligns with the research of Shahzadi, John, Qadeer, Jia, and Yan (2024), who argue that when CSR is perceived as merely symbolic and lacking substance, it can cause cognitive dissonance in the public, potentially leading to cynicism as a form of psychological defense.

The Role of CSR Process and Communication Model in CSR Innovation

CSR innovation refers to creative and novel approaches in the implementation of CSR, including innovation in processes, products, and stakeholder engagement (Pralhad et al., 2012).

CSR innovation generates added value for both the company and society. It is not only rooted in creativity but also shaped by research, stakeholder needs, and effective communication, ensuring that CSR programs are relevant, accepted, and impactful.

The CSR Process Model plays a crucial role in driving CSR innovation by offering a strategic framework for planning through to program evaluation (Altenburger, 2018). The *Creating the CSR Initiative* phase is the primary space where innovation emerges, fueled by formative research and monitoring. Meanwhile, the evaluation phase provides feedback to refine and develop future innovations based on the program’s impact.

According to Prahalad et al. (2012), CSR serves as a platform for innovation through four key dimensions known as the 4As:

1. **Awareness**, refers to the effort to build public consciousness about a product or service, including knowledge of its availability and how to use or access it. Interviews with various informants revealed the following:

Table 14: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Awareness

Participants	Comments
AN	“...we didn’t explicitly say that exchanging waste for milk was also a way to promote Entrasol milk... but the community already understood it...”
	“...we throw away trash... get milk for free... But it was Mr. Teo who bought the milk from us. So, the profit was deducted to purchase the milk.”
	“...we use social media, IG Live, digital platforms, websites... we share these programs, both the social and environmental ones...”
D	“Now it’s much easier; just turn on the faucet and water flows... we used to fight over water... now it flows every day.”

(Source: Author’s Compilation)

These statements reflect the company's efforts in building public awareness of the products, services, or programs, including how to access and engage with them:

- a) CSR initiatives build product awareness (without overt promotion). Although not directly advertised, Kalbe’s CSR programs effectively raised public awareness of the milk products used within the program.
- b) Communities understand how to participate and benefit. The CSR initiative was designed in a way that helped the public comprehend the "waste-for-milk" exchange system, increasing awareness of its mechanisms and benefits.
- c) Use of various media to enhance public awareness. Kalbe utilized multiple communication channels to raise awareness of their CSR programs.
- d) CSR programs introduced clean water services and how to access them. Communities that previously struggled with water scarcity are now aware of the new water facilities and how to use them.

Interview findings show that Kalbe, through its CSR programs, successfully increased public awareness of both services and products (e.g., clean water, milk), communicated how to participate and benefit, and used appropriate media platforms to broaden public understanding. These results align with findings by Gomez (2021), which emphasize the importance of proactively informing the public about CSR initiatives to foster loyalty and commitment toward corporate social and environmental responsibility efforts.

2. Access, refers to ensuring that products or services are reachable by all segments of society, including those in remote or underserved areas. Interviews with various informants revealed the following:

Table 15: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Access

Participants	Comments
D	<i>“...from the top of the hills... homes that used to fight over water... now water flows daily to their houses...”</i>
AN	<i>“...we built piping systems... reaching even distant villages... now they just turn on the tap and the water flows...”</i>
	<i>“...we developed a waste-for-milk system... so even those without money can access products by contributing waste.”</i>
	<i>“...we never donate cash... only in the form of goods and facilities, and the management is handled by the local community.”</i>

(Source: Author’s Compilation)

These excerpts indicate efforts by the company to ensure real access to services and products, even in remote or marginalized areas:

- a) The clean water program reaches hillside residents. This shows that access to clean water was successfully extended even to areas with difficult geographic conditions.
- b) Pipelines were built to reach remote regions. Infrastructure such as clean water pipelines demonstrates a tangible effort to expand access to essential services.

- c) Products were made accessible through inclusive mechanisms. Kalbe developed systems that allow even low-income individuals to participate, such as the exchange of waste instead of cash.
- d) Community participation without administrative or financial barriers. The programs are managed directly by residents, eliminating bureaucratic and financial hurdles in accessing benefits.

These interviews suggest that Kalbe effectively ensured broad and tangible access to its CSR services and products by overcoming geographic barriers (e.g., piping systems in hilly areas), creating inclusive models (e.g., waste exchange), and empowering community-led program management. These findings support Sayono et al. (2020), who argue that CSR-based community empowerment is not merely about direct aid, but about enabling communities to be self-sufficient and manage programs sustainably.

3. Affordability, refers to ensuring that products or services are offered at prices that are accessible to people from various socioeconomic backgrounds. Interviews with various informants revealed the following:

Table 16: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Affordability

Participants	Comments
AN	<i>“...we throw away waste... get milk for free... But it was Mr. Teo who purchased it from us. So, the profit was used to buy the milk.”</i>
	<i>“...we never donate money... everything must be managed by the community group... we only provide facilitation, not direct cash.”</i>
D	<i>“Mr. Theo and Kalbe needed manpower, and the women needed income. So, it was mutually beneficial... the women were enthusiastic too.”</i>
	<i>“...now water flows every day... previously we had to fight over it, now we just turn on the tap...”</i>

(Source: Author’s Compilation)

These excerpts highlight how Kalbe ensures that products or services can be accessed with minimal or no financial burden:

- a) Products are accessed free of charge through non-monetary contributions (waste exchange). Kalbe developed a waste-for-milk scheme, allowing people to access valuable products without spending money, making them extremely affordable—even free.
- b) The program is designed not to burden the community. Support is provided in the form of goods and infrastructure that can be directly utilized by the community without the need to purchase or pay.
- c) Contribution models are adapted to local economic conditions. Access to clean water—a basic need—is provided without mention of specific fees for residents, suggesting affordability or even free access.

Interview findings indicate that Kalbe’s CSR initiatives incorporate the principle of affordability through non-financial mechanisms such as waste exchange for goods, provision of essential services like clean water without user fees, and community empowerment as a form of non-financial contribution. These efforts are consistent with the findings of Rahi, Ahmad, & Sharma (2021), who emphasized the importance of creating supportive environments to overcome barriers in accessing essential services—through subsidies, community involvement, and enabling policies.

4. Availability, refers to ensuring that products and services are consistently accessible to maintain public trust and encourage long-term loyalty. Interviews with various informants revealed the following:

Table 17: Informants’ Perceptions on the Implementation of Availability

Participants	Comments
D	<i>“Now it’s much easier, we just turn on the tap and water flows... water now flows to their homes every day.”</i>
AN	<i>“...the milk is free... Mr. Teo is the one who buys it from us... so the system continues as long as people keep collecting waste.”</i>
	<i>“We don’t yet have an exit strategy for Wonogiri... in fact, we are still adding new social innovations there.”</i>
T	<i>“Every year, we always have activities... either training or motivation sessions... for the community and the association leaders.”</i>

(Source: Author’s Compilation)

These quotes show consistent efforts to maintain the availability of products and services to build public loyalty & trust:

- a) Clean water is available regularly and sustainably. This consistent access increases convenience and builds public trust in Kalbe’s CSR programs.
- b) Milk products remain available through the waste exchange system. This circulation mechanism ensures product availability as long as community participation continues.
- c) The program operates long-term without sudden exit strategies. Kalbe’s commitment to sustaining the program indicates long-term reliability, crucial for building public loyalty and trust.
- d) Regular provision of products and training sessions. Besides products, knowledge access and ongoing capacity building are also routinely provided to sustain community engagement and loyalty.

The findings show that Kalbe ensures the availability of essential services (e.g., daily water access), implements sustainable product distribution systems, avoids abrupt program discontinuation, and continuously provides community training. These aspects contribute to strengthening public trust and loyalty toward Kalbe’s CSR initiatives. This is in line with Servera-Francés and Piqueras-Tomás (2019), who argued that consistent and sustainable CSR

policies enhance consumer perceptions of company value and reinforce trust, commitment, satisfaction, and loyalty.

Effective communication significantly supports the adoption and public acceptance of CSR innovations (Rexhepi, Kurtishi, & Bexheti, 2013). *CSR Communication Factors* ensure that communications throughout the CSR process, especially when conveying initiatives, are conducted effectively and targeted appropriately. According to Huijstee and Glasbergen (2008, as cited in Dimitrova, 2020), a crucial aspect of the relationship between CSR and innovation lies in how companies engage with their stakeholders.

1. Companies must adopt a transparent and open approach by promoting shared values that unite all parties in an ongoing dialogue. Interviews and analysis indicate that transparency is a dominant dimension in Kalbe's CSR implementation. This reflects Kalbe's significant efforts to foster sustainable innovation through its CSR programs.
2. The company also acts as a bridge or mediator, helping convey and clarify key messages between the organization and stakeholders to achieve mutual understanding. Interview findings show that Kalbe fulfills this intermediary role by tailoring messages for both internal and external audiences, facilitating public forums and discussions, engaging directly in the field, and collaborating with local governments.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that Kalbe has implemented CSR innovations grounded in systematic social mapping and formative research. The process of identifying community needs (particularly in relation to clean water, health education, and waste management) has served as a crucial foundation for designing contextual and relevant programs.

The stages of scanning and formative research reflect an innovative approach that is attentive to local realities, ensuring that each CSR initiative is not merely symbolic but addresses the actual problems faced by the community. This affirms that Kalbe's CSR innovations are the result of a *bottom-up* approach that fosters sustainability from the planning stage.

In the *creating the CSR initiative* phase, Kalbe successfully formulated CSR programs in a structured, multi-tiered, and collaborative manner using the PDCA (Plan-Do-Check-Act) managerial framework. Programs such as water piping installation, health education, and the waste-for-milk exchange system exemplify social innovations that combine community empowerment with business strategy.

The application of the Creating Shared Value (CSV) concept ensures that the social and economic sustainability of the community becomes an integral part of the company's long-term sustainability. This reinforces the view of CSR not only as a social obligation, but as a core element of sustainable business strategy.

Findings also show that Kalbe has conducted CSR communication effectively by tailoring media and messages to suit its audiences. Transparency emerged as the most dominant dimension in the *communicating the CSR initiative* phase, with Kalbe not only highlighting its

achievements but also openly acknowledging its challenges and limitations. Kalbe's CSR communication is further strengthened by third-party endorsement, personal relevance, and active community participation (*self-efficacy*). This combination creates communication that is not only informative but also builds credibility and trust—key prerequisites for long-term sustainability.

Despite the strategic and multifaceted nature of Kalbe's CSR communication, frequency remains a weakness that needs to be addressed. Public fatigue or disengagement may arise due to a lack of variety in message delivery or unstructured communication rhythms.

Although Kalbe is aware of the risks of overexposure, there is still no clear evidence of a calendar-based communication system or thematic campaigns to sustain public interest in the long term. Therefore, sustaining CSR innovation also requires communication strategies that are adaptable to audience dynamics and timing.

Overall, Kalbe's CSR efforts have successfully demonstrated that social innovations, in the form of environmental programs and community empowerment, can serve as vehicles for corporate sustainability. By integrating the 4A principles (Awareness, Access, Affordability, Availability) into program implementation and reinforcing them with strong CSR communication (especially transparency), Kalbe shows that sustainability can be achieved not only through profitability but also through strong relationships with the community. This reinforces the notion that effectively communicated CSR innovation is a fundamental pillar of a sustainable company.

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References

- 1) Altenburger, R. (2018). Corporate Social Responsibility as a Driver of Innovation Processes. In R. Altenburger (Ed.), *Innovation Management and Corporate Social Responsibility: Social Responsibility as Competitive Advantage* (pp. 1–12). Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93629-1_1
- 2) Aurelia, A., Arismayanti, P., & Anggraini, C. (2023). *Analisis Strategi Komunikasi CSR Melalui Media Digital dalam Menciptakan Keberlanjutan Perusahaan*.
- 3) Bagherzadeh, N., & Manoli, C. (2012). *CSR Activities Promotes Sustainability A case study of Bombardier*.
- 4) Coombs, W. T., & Holladay, S. J. (2011). Conceptualizing Corporate Social Responsibility. In *Managing Corporate Social Responsibility* (pp. 1–27). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118106686.ch1>
- 5) Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Method Approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- 6) Dahono, Y. (2023, July 6). Komitmen Jalankan Program Keberlanjutan, Kalbe Raih Penghargaan Platinum dan Gold ISRA 2023.
- 7) Dimitrova, Y. (n.d.). Corporate Social Responsibility and Innovation-the Meaningfull Connection Corporate Social Responsibility And Innovation-The Meaningful Connection. In *Yanica P. Dimitrova* (Vol. 1). Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343291411>

- 8) Ernawati, E. (2022). Pengaruh Implementasi Corporate Social Responsibility (Csr) Terhadap Peningkatan Citra Pt. Semen Tonasa Di Desa Bulu Cindea Kecamatan Bungoro Kabupaten Pangkep. *Ecotechnopreneur : Journal Economics, Technology And Entrepreneur*, 1(03), 216–241. <https://doi.org/10.62668/ecotechnopreneur.v1i03.254>
- 9) Gomez, L. M. (2021). The State of Social Media Research in CSR Communication. In D. Crowther & S. Seifi (Eds.), *The Palgrave Handbook of Corporate Social Responsibility* (pp. 577–598). Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-42465-7_66
- 10) Intani, R. (2018). *Strategi Public Relations Pt. Pelni (Persero) Mengimplementasi Program Csr Melalui Program Kemitraan Dan Bina Lingkungan*.
- 11) Kalbe Farma. (2021). *2021 Sustainable Report*. Jakarta. Retrieved from www.kalbe.co.id/api-content/File/GetFile/SR%20PT%20Kalbe%20Farma%20Tbk%20English.pdf
- 12) Kim, H., & Lee, T. H. (2018). Strategic CSR Communication: A Moderating Role of Transparency in Trust Building. *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, 12(2), 107–124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1553118X.2018.1425692>
- 13) Kim, S. (2019). The Process Model of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Communication: CSR Communication and its Relationship with Consumers' CSR Knowledge, Trust, and Corporate Reputation Perception. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 154(4), 1143–1159. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-017-3433-6>
- 14) Kiroyan, N. (2019, February). Mengomunikasikan CSR. *PR INDONESIA*, 47.
- 15) Lim, J. S., & Jiang, H. (2021). Linking Authenticity in CSR Communication to Organization-Public Relationship Outcomes: Integrating Theories of Impression Management and Relationship Management. *Journal of Public Relations Research*, 33(6), 464–486. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1062726X.2022.2048953>
- 16) Nurozi, K., & Sisdiyanto, E. (2024). Peran Corporate Social Responsibility (Csr) Dalam Meningkatkan Kesejahteraan Masyarakat: Analisis Dampak Sosial Dan Ekonomi. *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Manajemen*, 2(11), 301–315.
- 17) Octaviani, F., Raharjo, S. T., & Resnawaty, R. (2022). Strategi Komunikasi dalam Corporate Social Responsibility Perusahaan sebagai upaya Pemberdayaan Masyarakat. *Jurnal Ilmu Kesejahteraan Sosial HUMANITAS*. Retrieved from <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:257059501>
- 18) Prahalad, C. K., Di Benedetto, A., & Nakata, C. (2012). Bottom of the pyramid as a source of breakthrough innovations. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 29(1), 6–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5885.2011.00874.x>
- 19) Pratiwi, F. (2023, March 8). Kalbe Farma Sediakan Akses Air Bersih di Wonogiri.
- 20) Rahi, M., Ahmad, S. S., & Sharma, A. (2021). Coverage enhancement and community empowerment via commercial availability of the long-lasting nets for malaria in India. *Public Health in Practice*, 2, 100133. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhip.2021.100133>
- 21) Rexhepi, G., Kurtishi, S., & Bexheti, G. (2013). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Innovation—The Drivers of Business Growth? *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 75, 532–541. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.04.058>
- 22) Riano, J. D., & Yakovleva, N. (2020). *Corporate Social Responsibility*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-95726-5_26
- 23) Rutledge, P. B., & Hogg, J. L. C. (2020). In-Depth Interviews. In *The International Encyclopedia of Media Psychology* (pp. 1–7). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119011071.iemp0019>

- 24) Saleh, A., & Sihite, M. (2020). Strategi Komunikasi untuk Program Corporate Social Responsibility dalam Pemberdayaan Masyarakat. *Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi*, 4(1), 98–105. <https://doi.org/10.30596/interaksi.v4i1.4134>
- 25) Sayono, J., Taufiq, A., Sringernyuang, L., Alif Haji Sismat, M., Ismail, Z., Navarro, F. M., & Purnomo, A. (2020). *Community Empowerment Through Research, Innovation And Open Access*.
- 26) Sendlhofer, T., & Tolstoy, D. (2022). How employees shape CSR transparency: A sensemaking perspective. *Journal of Business Research*, 150, 268–278. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.05.074>
- 27) Servera-Francés, D., & Piqueras-Tomás, L. (2019). The effects of corporate social responsibility on consumer loyalty through consumer perceived value. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 32(1), 66–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2018.1547202>
- 28) Shahzadi, G., John, A., Qadeer, F., Jia, F., & Yan, J. (2024). CSR beyond symbolism: The importance of substantive attributions for employee CSR engagement. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 436, 140440. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.140440>
- 29) Syahrhani, D., Siwi, M., Manusia, F. E., Pertanian Bogor, I., Departemen, D., Komunikasi, S., & Masyarakat, P. (2018). *Hubungan Komunikasi Corporate Social Responsibility dengan Citra Perusahaan*. *Jurnal Komunikasi Pembangunan* (Vol. 16).
- 30) Syaifudin, A. A., Tinggi, S., Islam, A., Bojonegoro, A., Rista, D., & Tinggi, S. S. (2023). Implementasi dan Peran Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) terhadap Kepercayaan Anggota KSPPS BMT NU Balen Cabang Sugihwaras Bojonegoro. *Al-Muraqabah: Journal of Management and Sharia Business*, 3(1), 22–41. Retrieved from <https://jurnalfebi.iainkediri.ac.id/index.php/muraqabah>
- 31) Taherdoost, H. (2020). Different Types of Data Analysis; Data Analysis Methods and Techniques in Research Projects. In *International Journal of Academic Research in Management (IJARM)* (Vol. 9). Retrieved from www.elvedit.com
- 32) Taliding, A. (2021). Evaluasi Efektivitas Corporate Social Responsibility Pada Pt Semen Tonasa (Studi Kasus Pada Pt Semen Tonasa). In *Jurnal Online Manajemen Elpei (Jomel)* (Vol. 1). Retrieved from <http://jurnal.stim-lpi.ac.id/index.php/elpei>
- 33) Willya Achmad, R. W. (2021). Monitoring Dan Evaluasi Program Corporate Social Responsibility Berbasis Pemberdayaan Masyarakat. In *Komitmen: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen* (Vol. 2).